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Assessment Of Awareness, Access And Utilization Of Library Resource Among People With Special Needs In Tertiary Institutions

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ABSTRACT

The study is on the Assessment of Awareness, Access and Utilization of library resources among people with special needs in colleges of education libraries in the three north-western states of Nigeria (Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara) states. The survey technique was employed in the study. Three states owned colleges of education selected are Adamu Augie college of education Shehu Shagari college of education and Maru college of education. The population of the study comprise all the library staff and the students with special needs in the colleges under review which amounted to 103 as the entire population of the study. Structured questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection and descriptive statistics was used to analyze data. The study found that among other things Utilization of library resources remains low due to a combination of limited awareness, accessibility barriers, and insufficient staff training in supporting individuals with special needs, this underutilization highlights a gap between the availability of resources and their effective use. In lights of the forgoing the study recommended that there should be a provision of regular awareness campaigns and training for library staff on how to support individuals with special needs effectively.

Keywords: Awareness, Access, Utilization and special needs.

INTRODUCTION

Formally, libraries are designed as service center organizations which facilitates all their users with accessible, current and relevant information resources without discrimination including people with special needs. This is because these category of learners have constituted a population size in our schools and colleges demanding all forms of considerations to participate fully in the academic pursuance. In a related development, World Health Organization and World Bank (2011) stated that 15% of the total world population is suffering from some kind of special needs (Papworth Trust 2011). Moreover, the United Nation Organization states that persons with special needs should live independently and contribute fully to all facet of life. State institutions should take suitable measures to ensure the access with persons with special disabilities on equal basis. These measures should include the identification and elimination of obstacles and barriers to accessibility to physical environment, to transportation and to Information and Communication Technology. (UNO, 2006). Similarly, the convention on the right of people with disabilities (CRPD, 2008) suggested that “The purpose of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) is to promote, protect and ensure the full and equal

enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms by all persons with disabilities, and to promote respect for their inherent dignity” As such it therefore becomes necessary for our educational system designers, planners, administrators and stakeholders to redouble their efforts in ameliorating all issues regarding people with special needs in their educational pursuance.

However, professional educators tend to classify people with special needs by the degree of their disabilities. The magnitude of disability differs from one group to another, ranging from blindness, deafness, crippled persons, and the mentally retarded, etc. Often, the terms of impairment, physically challenged, handicapped, disabled, and special needs persons are used interchangeably. Everyone is expected to conform to certain physical standard. Special needs students are either placed in special schools or classes or totally excluded from any educational opportunity mostly in our rural areas on the ground that they are disabled which is against the global practices. Furthermore, everyone has certain abilities that can, with appropriate education and training, be developed to their maximum capability in respective of his/her physical outlook. Individual disability should not be a barrier, it is necessary to provide information resources and services to all forms of learners. Affix to say that the established laws that states the individual rights and privileges does not discriminate in all aspect (social rights, political rights, and educational rights).

The library system in any organizational setting is a repository of information resources. Its major functions include the collection, organization, storage, and dissemination of information to the user. It is therefore necessary to equip our academic libraries with all forms of information resources accessible to all kind of users who got opportune to be part of the system so as to contribute their own quota to the societal development. Moreover, a recent survey to states own collages of education (Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara) states has indicates that such conventional institutional libraries are well stocked with information resources capable of excelling in teaching learning and research mostly for normal students (Category A) with little or no required provision for people with special needs (category B) who coincidentally happens to be part and parcel of the systems they found themselves. On the side of the library services, little attention was observed also to be given on training and retraining of library staff who are to cater for special needs groups.

Problem Statement

A preliminary survey indicates that there is little or no record of Awareness, Access and proffer Utilization of library resources in the conventional academic institutional libraries meant to be use among some categories of students (persons with special needs) who are part and parcel of the library users despite the financial and material support it receives from government in form of grants or intervention (annual/special) from tetfund and other agencies.

It is loud and clear that the ideal function of an academic library is to cater for all its client/users regardless of their physical structures, gender or physical fitness. A library should be well planned and designed environment (Building structure), user friendly facilities and systems with conducive learning environment with specially trained professional staff so as to accomplish the objectives of its parent organization by catering for all categories of users who should be train to excel in different areas of human endeavor through teaching learning and research.

Moreover, a well equip library in an academic system contributes in equal proportion with classroom activities in making learners to excel in teaching, learning and research. This is justifiable when learners tend to find it difficult to survive in their academic pursuit on a system with no relevant and accessible information resources, the effect of which would turn the remaining abilities in to more serious learning disabilities to the concern category. To investigate this problem is what has drawn the attention of the researchers to undergo this study so as to identify and recommends proper solution.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to assess the awareness, access and utilization of library resources among the people with special needs (The physically challenged and those with vision/hearing impairment) in relation to its effect on products and services delivery to those category of library users

which adversely affect their performances in teaching, learning and research processes and proffer the alternative solutions to problems identified.

Objectives of the Research

The following specific objectives were used to guide study:

1. To examine the level of awareness of library resources on people with special needs in the institutional libraries of Adamu Augie, Shehu Shagari and Maru Colleges of Education.
2. To investigate the mode of access to library resources on people with special needs in the aforementioned institutional libraries.
3. To assess the nature of the library trained staff and resources available to cater for people with special needs in those institutional libraries.
4. To examine the frequency of use of library resources by people with special needs in those Colleges libraries.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of library resources designed for people with special needs in Adamu Augie, Shehu Shagari and Maru Colleges of education?
2. What are the mode of access to library resources among people with special needs in those institutional libraries?
3. What is the availability of specially trained staff and library resources procured for people with special needs in the concerned institutions?
4. What are the frequency of use of library resources among people with special needs in the mentioned institutional libraries?

Delimitation/Scope

The study is designed to cover the institutional libraries of Adamu Augie College of education, Argungu, Kebbi state. Shehu Shagari College of education Sokoto, Sokoto state and Maru College of education, Zamfara, Zamfara state in the northwestern part of Nigeria using the entire library staff and the available admitted special students (physically challenge) of the institutions as the respondents (primary source of data).

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study intends to review relevant literature in the area of Awareness, access and utilization of library resources among people with special needs in tertiary institutions. However, few literatures are presented to represent the type of literatures expected to be reviewed.

A study conducted by Bodaghi & Zainab (2013) has explored the views of architects and library users with physical disabilities regarding the accessibility to library buildings and equipment's in Iran. The sample for the study was 150 among which 142 responses were considered usable. The age of the participants was between 15 and 40 years. 49.6 % of the participants were wheel-chair users, 46.4% used canes or crutches and 4 % did not indicate their use of equipment. The educational level of respondents, varied from completing high school to university education. 14 libraries which consisted of seven public and seven university libraries in Zanjan Province were chosen for the study. A total of 13 architects were requested to observe and evaluate the selected libraries. The results of the study conclude that the accessibility of the libraries was not rated as 'good' neither by the disabled users nor the architects. The disabled users have also highlighted the related issues like availability of parking spaces, ramps and exclusive spaces as posing difficulties for them in accessing library services. Additionally, the interior layout and public space of the libraries were regarded as less challenging. Phukubje & Ngoepe (2016) have done a study in South Africa to assess the convenience and accessibility of library services for students with disabilities at University of Limpopo. The study has also examined the other aspects like services offered, physical access and availability of study material for students with disabilities. They have found that the students with disabilities were not satisfied with the library services, majorly because only a few library materials were transcribed into accessible formats. The other problems reported by the

participants of this study included the inadequate training in how to use the library, restricted library opening hours and inaccessible formats. Carter (2004) in her work has discussed three areas where librarians can focus so as to meet the needs of students with disabilities. These have been presented as bibliographic instruction, web pages and staff training. The author has examined the possibilities of providing enhanced services to students with disabilities. The paper has also stressed on evaluating library services periodically as new technologies keep on emerging. The author has also explored the possibility of 'adapting a multi-sensory teaching style that uses a variety of visual, aural, and tactile techniques meets the needs of every kind of learner'. A study has been conducted by Ekwelem (2013) to assess the use of electronic media by disabled library users in South-east Nigeria. The participants of the study were 184 disabled library users in which 101 were having visual impairment and 93 were having physical impairment. The findings reveal that the taped books and online public access catalogue (OPAC) were the only electronic resources available to the library users with visual impairments. The participants of this study have perceived that the libraries were established to cater to the needs of non-disabled users. The findings have also revealed that there is limited knowledge of the needs of persons with disabilities. Oswal (2017) in his work has tried to analyze the impact of accessibility barriers of libraries on disabled students' ability to succeed. The author has particularly focused on the accessibility challenges faced by users with visual and hand-motor disabilities who have frequently been excluded by the policy makers, library planners and software developers. This work has provided a glimpse regarding the accessibility issues and their impact on various dimensions of disabled person's lives like employability, the accessibility barriers embedded in research data bases and e-books. The author has stressed on the importance of engaging the actual stakeholders i.e., the disabled users in both the design and development stages of the platforms, user interfaces and content presentation scheme. Information has long been recognized as important resources for national development. Access, or lack of it, to information could have a significant effect on the success or failure of individuals in solving problems or enhancing their life opportunities. Information is an important resource for development and should be considered as a prerequisite for sound decision in all areas of activities, research and development, academic, planning, industrial development, and investment. The most critical commodity influencing changes in the urban situation is information. In the view of Ajibero (2000), "information value is frequently expressed as a derivation from communication utility" (p. 3). Abdulahi (2000) observed that companies that are committed to customers are interested in what customers think and feel, and therefore, make conscious efforts to track down information about customers' needs, aspirations, behaviors, and preferences. He further stressed that marketing personnel relies more on data and information to get a better understanding of the marketing issues before deciding on a course of action. Information is needed at every level of business activities. It is required for policy formulation, planning and implementation of policy objective. The increased and increasing importance of information in that was stressed by Bell (1976), "A post-industrial society is basically an information society. Exchange of information in terms of various kinds of data processing, record keeping, market research and so forth is the foundation of most economic changes" (p. 46). Information is a vital resource for everyone. The library must find and select the most profitably useful information for its clients. Mbeki (1997) stressed that "The concept of a caring society is strengthened and deepened when we recognize that disabled people enjoy the same rights as we do and that we have a responsibility towards the promotion of their quality of life". In Nigeria, although there is constitutional provision for the education of the special needs persons, it is philanthropic organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and private and missionary schools, rather than the National Library of Nigeria, that have faced the challenges of providing reading materials to the special needs persons. Aina (2004) opined that many studies in Africa have revealed that these groups of users are not catered for by almost all types of libraries. Only in those libraries that are specifically devoted to this group of users will one find most of the equipment and materials, like Braille, that the users require (p. 6).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology to be adopted is a survey method using a (case study) with a structured questionnaire designed and modified to fit the study for data collection. The dependents and independent variables were captured in the questionnaire and the data were analyzed quantitatively. The procedure for data analysis in this research is the use of descriptive statistical tools, the use of frequency distribution table will also be employed. However, the population of this study is the entire library staff and students (people with special needs) from three selected colleges of education (Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu, Kebbi state. Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Sokoto state and College of Education Maru, Zamfara state which amounted to 107 (one hundred and seven) all together i.e. staff and as primary sources of data while resources serve as secondary source. There is no need of involving sampling technique hence the data is manageable. For the data analyses, we involve the use of software package for social sciences called SPSS.

However, Survey is a form of research used when dealing with very systematic collection of data or information from population or sample of a population. Ndagi (2011) stated that survey research method is concerned with collection of data for the purpose of describing, interpreting existing conditions, prevailing practice, beliefs or ongoing process. The survey method for this work aimed at surveying the aforementioned institutional libraries by the researchers to draw raw data from the targeted population.

RESULTS

Table 4.1 To what extent are you aware of the library resources specifically designed for people with disabilities

Item	Frequency	Percent
Not at all aware	42	40.7
Somewhat aware	59	57.4
Very aware	2	1.9
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field Data (2024)

The table above show the respondents opinion on the awareness of the library resources specifically designed for people with disability, the finding above shows that 59 (57.4%) are somewhat aware that library resources specifically designed for people with disability, 42 (40.7%) are not at all aware, while 2 (1.9%) are very aware on the issue. the finding above shows that majority of the respondents are somewhat aware that library resources specifically designed for people with disability with the highest percentage of 57.4%.

Table 4.2 What types of library resources for people with disabilities are you aware of

Item	Frequency	Percent
Assistive technology	41	39.3
Accessible formats	32	32.0
Sign language interpretation	17	16.5
Braille materials	13	12.2
Total	103	100.0

Table 4.2 above show the respondents opinion on what types of library resources for people with disabilities are you aware of, the finding above shows that 41 (39.3%) are aware of assistive technology, 32 (32%) accessible formats, 17 (16.5%) sign language interpretation while 13 (12.2%) use braille

materials. The finding above shows that majority of the respondents are on of assistive technology with the highest percentage of 39.3%.

Table 4.3 How do you typically access library resources?

Item	Frequency	Percent
A Physical library visit	54	52.4
Online Access	32	31.2
Assistive Technology	11	10.6
Personal assistance	6	5.8
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field data (2024)

The table above show the respondents opinion on how do you typically access library resources, the finding above shows that 54 (52.4%) are on physical library visit, 32 (31.2%) use online, 11 (10.6%) use assistive technology while 6 (5.8%) use personal assistance. The findings above shows that majority of the respondents use physical library visit with the highest percentage of 52.4%.

Table 4.4 What specific challenges do you face in accessing library resources

Item	Frequency	Percent
Lack of accessibility features	35	33.9
Limited availability of accessible formats	62	60.3
Insufficient staff training	6	5.8
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field data (2024)

Table above show the respondent opinion whether there is specific challenges do you face in accessing library resources, the finding above shows that 62 (60.3%) have limited availability of accessible format, 35 (33.9%) lack of accessibility features while 6 (5.8%) have insufficient staff training. The finding above shows that majority of the respondents are having challenges of accessing Library resources.

Table 4.5 Do you feel that library staff are adequately trained to assist students with disabilities

Item	Frequency	Percent
Strongly disagree	15	14.5
Disagree	19	18.4
Neither agree nor disagree	21	20.3
Strongly agree	48	46.8
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field data (2024)

Table above show the respondents opinion wether they feel that library staff are adequately trained to assist students with disabilities, the finding above shows that 46 (46.8%) strongly agreed on the issue that feel that library staff are adequately trained to assist students with disabilities, 21 (20.3%) neither agree nor disagree, 19 (18.4%) disagreed while 15 (14.5%) strongly disagreed on the issue. The finding above shows that majority of the respondents are in the agreement on the issue that feel that library staff are adequately trained to assist students with disabilities with the highest percentage of 46.8%.

Table 4.6 Have you encountered any difficulties in receiving assistance from library staff due to your disability

Item	Frequency	Percent
Unsatisfied service	35	33.9
Disregard	62	60.3
Little or no attention	6	5.8
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field data (2024)

Table above show the difficulties encounter in receiving assistance from library staff due to your disability, this shows that 62 (60.3%) disregard difficulties in receiving assistance from library staff due to disability, 35 (33.9%) unsatisfied service, while 6 (5.8%) receive little or no attention. The finding above shows that majority of the respondents challenges is on the disregard issue that difficulties in receiving assistance from library staff due to your disability with the highest percentage of 60.3%.

Table 4.7 Are you satisfied with the availability of library resources specifically designed for students with disabilities

Item	Frequency	Percent
Strongly disagree	14	13.4
Disagree	13	12.6
Neither agree nor disagree	22	21.6
Strongly agree	54	52.4
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field data (2024)

The table above show the respondents opinion on whether they are satisfied with the availability of library resources specifically designed for students with disabilities, this show that 54 (52.4%) strongly agreed on the issue that they are satisfied with the availability of library resources specifically designed for students with disabilities, 22 (21.6%) neither agree nor disagree, 14 (13.4%) strongly disagreed while 13 (12.6%) disagreed on the issue. The finding above shows that majority of the respondent are on the agreement with the issue that, are you satisfied with the availability of library resources specifically designed for students with disabilities with the highest percentage of 52.4%.

Table 4.8 What kind of specific library resources for students with disabilities are you currently using

Item	Frequency	Percent
Accessible formats	61	59.9
Sign language	33	32.0
Braille materials	9	8.1
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field data (2024)

Table showing the respondent opinion whether specific library resources for students with disabilities are you currently using, this shows that 61 (59.9%) have accessible formats of library resources for students with disabilities, 33 (32%) use sign language, while 9 (8.1%) use braille materials. The finding above shows that majority of the respondents are using accessible formats for accessing library resources for students with disabilities currently using with the highest percentage of 59.9%.

Table 4.9 How often do you use library resources

Item	Frequency	Percent
Daily	37	35.1
Weekly	42	40.7
Monthly	15	14.5
Occasionally	9	8.7
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field data (2024)

Table above show how often do you use library resources, the finding above shows that 42 (40.7%) use library weekly, 37 (35.1%) daily, 15 (14.5%) monthly while 9 (8.7%) use it occasionally. The finding above shows that majority of the respondents are making the use of library weekly due to the time factor with the highest percentage of 40.7%.

Table 4.10 What factors influence your frequency of use of library resources

Item	Frequency	Percent
Accessibility of resources	51	49.5
Convenience	26	25.3
Personal needs	6	5.8
Availability of assistance	20	19.4
Total	103	100.0

Source: Field data (2024)

The table above show the factors that influence frequency of use of library resources, the result show that 51 (49.5%) respondents' frequency of use of the library resources is influence by the accessibility to the resources factor, 26 (25.3%) convenience, 20 (19.4%) availability of assistance while 6 (5.8%) personal needs. The finding above shows that majority of the respondents frequency of use is influence by access of use of library resources with the highest percentage of 49.5%.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The assessment of awareness, access, and utilization of library resources among people with special needs in Northwestern State's colleges of education in Nigeria reveals significant findings that underscore both the challenges and opportunities present in academic libraries. These findings are critical in understanding how libraries can better serve individuals with disabilities, ensuring equitable access to educational resources.

One of the primary findings is the level of awareness regarding available library resources. Studies indicate that while many users are aware of the resources offered, there remains a significant gap in the actual utilization of these resources. For instance, Eyiolorunshe and Eluwole found that despite high awareness levels among faculty members at Landmark University, the utilization of available resources was notably low, particularly for electronic resources (Eyiolorunshe & Eluwole, 2017). This trend suggests that awareness alone does not translate into usage, highlighting the need for targeted user education and outreach programs to bridge this gap (Eyiolorunshe & Eluwole, 2017; Shah & Idrees, 2021).

Access to library resources is another critical area of concern. Research indicates that individuals with special needs often face barriers that hinder their ability to fully utilize library services. Hamam emphasizes the importance of integrating assistive technologies, such as screen readers and specialized keyboards, to enhance access for persons with disabilities (Hamam, 2023). Furthermore, the study by Phukubje and Ngoepe highlights that students with disabilities require tailored access solutions, which are often lacking in many academic libraries (Phukubje & Ngoepe, 2016). This lack of adequate access

not only affects the utilization of resources but also impacts the overall educational experience for these students.

Moreover, the role of library staff in promoting awareness and facilitating access cannot be overstated. Effective marketing strategies and user education initiatives are essential for increasing the visibility of library resources among students with special needs. Shah and Idrees argue that libraries must actively promote their services to enhance user awareness and satisfaction (Shah & Idrees, 2021). This includes developing specific outreach programs that cater to the unique needs of individuals with disabilities, as well as ensuring that library staff are trained to assist these users effectively (Kumbier & Starkey, 2016). In addition to awareness and access, the integration of inclusive practices within library services is crucial. Majinge and Msonge advocate for the inclusion of special needs considerations in library and information science curricula to prepare future librarians to better serve this demographic (Majinge & Msonge, 2020). This approach not only fosters a more inclusive library environment but also ensures that library services are designed with the needs of all users in mind.

In conclusion, the assessment of awareness, access, and utilization of library resources among people with special needs in Northwestern State's colleges of education reveals a complex interplay of factors that influence library engagement. While awareness of resources is relatively high, actual utilization remains low due to accessibility barriers and insufficient promotional efforts. Libraries must prioritize the integration of assistive technologies, enhance marketing strategies, and foster inclusive practices to ensure that all users, particularly those with disabilities, can fully benefit from library services.

CONCLUSION

The research on the Assessment of Awareness, Access, and Utilization of Library Resources Among People with Special Needs in Northwestern States' Colleges of Education (Kebbi, Sokoto and Zamfara) highlights critical findings regarding the level of inclusion and accessibility in academic libraries.

1. The study revealed that while there is a moderate level of awareness of library resources among people with special needs, this awareness is primarily limited to a few specific resources. Many individuals remain unaware of specialized services and assistive technologies available to support their learning needs.
2. Access to library resources for people with special needs is hindered by infrastructural, technological, and environmental barriers. Challenges such as inadequate ramps, absence of Braille materials, and lack of adaptive technology significantly limit their ability to utilize library services effectively.
3. Utilization of library resources remains low due to a combination of limited awareness, accessibility barriers, and insufficient staff training in supporting individuals with special needs. This underutilization highlights a gap between the availability of resources and their effective use.
4. Colleges of Education in Zamfara and Sokoto states show varying degrees of commitment to inclusivity. However, the overall lack of dedicated policies, funding, and training programs to enhance accessibility and inclusivity in libraries contributes to the observed challenges.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Conduct targeted awareness campaigns and outreach programs to inform people with special needs about available library resources and services.
2. Enhance physical and digital infrastructure in libraries to ensure compliance with universal design standards.
3. Provide regular training for library staff on how to support individuals with special needs effectively.
4. Establish clear policies and allocate funding to improve access and ensure sustainable inclusion practices in libraries.

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A SAMPLED QUESTIONNAIRE

ASSESSMENT OF AWARENESS, ACCESS AND UTILIZATION OF LIBRARY RESOURCE AMONG PEOPLE WITH SPECIAL NEEDS IN NORTHWESTERN STATE'S COLLEGES OF EDUCATION (SOKOTO, KEBBI AND ZAMFARA)

Dear respondent,

This questionnaire is strictly for research purposes. Your response shall be treated with utmost confidence. Thanks.

SECTION A PERSONAL DATA

1. Name of institution.....
2. Position...../ Level.....
3. Department/unit.....

SECTION B QUESTIONS. Instruction: Please tick the appropriate option in the list of options provided:

Awareness of Library Resources:

1. To what extent are you aware of the library resources specifically designed for people with disabilities?
A Not at all aware () B Somewhat aware () C Very aware ()

A Not at all aware () B Somewhat aware () C Very aware ()

2. What types of library resources for people with disabilities are you aware of? A Assistive technology B Accessible formats C Sign language interpretation D Braille materials ()

Modes of Access:

3. How do you typically access library resources? A Physical library visit B Online Access C Assistive Technology D Personal assistance

4. What specific challenges do you face in accessing library resources? A Lack of accessibility features () B Limited availability of accessible formats () C Insufficient staff training ()

Availability of Trained Staff:

5. Do you feel that library staff are adequately trained to assist students with disabilities? A Strongly disagree () B Disagree () C Neither agree nor disagree () D Strongly agree ()

6. Have you encountered any difficulties in receiving assistance from library staff due to your disability? A Unsatisfied service () B Disregard () C Little or no attention

Availability of Resources:

7. Are you satisfied with the availability of library resources specifically designed for students with disabilities? A Strongly disagree () B Disagree () C Neither agree nor disagree () D Agree strongly ()

8. What specific library resources for students with disabilities are you currently using? A Assistive technology () B Accessible formats () C Sign language interpretation () D Braille materials ()

Frequency of Use:

9. How often do you use library resources? A Daily () B Weekly () C Monthly () D Occasionally ()

10. What factors influence your frequency of use of library resources? A Accessibility of resources () B Convenience () C Personal needs () D Availability of assistance

Thank you for your cooperation.